

Mathematical Foundations of Abrahamic Holy Books under their Algebraic Structure (Letter Theory)

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Abstract:

This paper is an interdisciplinary work between theology (Abrahamic religions), linguistics (computational linguistics) and mathematics (mostly fractal geometry and abstract algebra) that tries to establish a letter system to define word meanings by letter meanings and to restart mathematical theology (~Algebraic theology) that I think had been started by Abraham the prophet.

We try to answer this question that can we create a meaning system which every alphabet letter has a specific meaning in, and when we combine them to create words we have a clear system to define every word's meaning just by its letters' meaning and order of those letters in the word? (I mean: Is alphabet set under a specific relation, an algebraic structure? As we know Any set, with a rule (or rules) for combining its elements, is already an algebraic structure.)

We will show that if we have a fractal system we can establish a letter system for it.

The other question that I try to answer is that can we produce a letter system that provides us with provable sentences?

At last, we show that Abrahamic holy books have a letter system and even if they have not; the fundamental correspondence shows that we can create one for them.

This paper shows that theology should be assumed as a sub-field of science and

mathematics; and mathematicians (letter theorists) should work on the field.

Introduction:

In the paper we discuss with three methods: 1: What's the theory according to sepher yetzirah 2: What's the theory according to holy books (Abrahamic letter system and finding meaning and rules of letters that exist in holy books 3: What's the theory if there is no theory in sepher yetzirah and holy books (We want to create it)

Before the alphabet's invention human used to write every word by a specific shape so they needed thousands of shapes to learn the writing and reading of their inscriptions; Until the alphabet was invented and they used just about 20 to 30 letters to write what they wanted.

What we want to do here is exactly something like that, but about the meaning system and not about the writing system (We already have it by alphabet invention); So the main question is:

Can we create a meaning system which every alphabet letter has a specific meaning in, and when we combine them to create words we have a clear system to define every word's meaning just by its letters meaning and the order of those letters in the word?

We will show that if we have a fractal system we can establish a letter system for it. (And also show that Abrahamic holy books have conditions of having a letter system).

The other question is: Can we produce a letter system that provides us with provable sentences?

We introduce some axioms which we need to have a good system and as a result, we show that by three axioms we will have a fractal language.

Maybe at first, it seems an ambitious work but I think we already use similar methods to mean words in dictionaries. For example, when we want to define apple we say it's a red and circle fruit. Circle, red and fruit are major words here, we use them in lots of places in dictionaries and are major elements. However dictionaries use just a method and have not a system to define; But our work searches for a system.

Sibawayhi and Alkhalil works show some fundamentals of how Arabic creates words from roots (Bohas 2016)^[6] and now we want to work on how roots have been created under the system of letters.

This paper is the first of my works that I publish to show the mathematical foundation

of Abrahamic religions and holy books and to start mathematical theology and I think science needs to have mathematical foundations to be understood. Here I just try to show the theory and not the documents, evidence and operations that I have done on holy books.

Importance:

_When we succeed will not need any dictionary anymore, and we just need to know the meaning of our letters and the letter system to know every word's meaning.

_It will be a useful way to teach robots an expandable language and they will can create infinite words and meanings by using the letter system (NLP).

_Our conjecture is that holy books have been based on a letter system and by exploring the system we can understand the real meaning of holy books.

_We establish a mathematical way to prove our sentences in our new language.

_This theory can establish mathematical fundamental structures for human sciences like what Isaac Newton did about physics in his book Principia ^[7].

_This theory contains important ideas for making algebra a self-similar object and its useful for developing algebra (For example our set is set of letters but letters can make numbers and numbers must be true under our letter equations so we have two isomorphic way to work with numbers).

When we talk about proofs here, most of the time we are talking about pre-proofs (pre-proof/proof=designing/painting).

Inspiration:

These are my questions about holy books which provided me to work on the theory of letters:

How does a prophet understand the meaning of a holy text he has received?

How does he prove that he is right and his texts come from the holy spirit?

How does he understand the meaning of words?

What's the meaning of Muqatta'at (Disconnected letters) of Quran?

When I was reading Arabic I found a special relation between its words' roots for example:

Quran, 96:4: who taught by the pen.

الذِي عَلَّمَ بِالْقَلَمِ

taught root is OLM and pen root is QLM.

Quran, 21:30: were stitched together, then We ripped them apart

كَانَتَا رَتْقًا فَفَقَتْنَا

The stitched root is RTQ and the ripped root is FTQ.

Probably others refer these to rhymes and Stylistic devices but it made me curious to work on them and made this question for me:

What if there is a relationship between the letters which we see in these kind of words?

I checked it in so many examples and it made me a conjecture:

Letters have meaning and combining them under a defined system makes words meanings.

I found some articles that have some similar and useful evidence that prepares to hear the main theory that I point to, for example: in the article of Stekel and co-authors 2023^[1] and probably in similar articles you can see lots of kad (neighbor) words that have kad meanings and it seems there are some useful works that have pointed to evidences that I have seen.

After years I found a book that maybe be a meaningless book for most of us. The book (Sepher Yezirah) was about combining letters but strongly was an abstract book and hard to understand for someone who does not know anything about letter theory. I read there that the book belongs to Abraham the prophet^[2] so I called the system that I read there the Abrahamic letter system.

Reading first sentences of Genesis of the Hebrew Bible made me think that Hebrew and Arabic have had a same language with a same letter system. So I assumed the Abrahamic letter system as an Arabic letter system and as all Abrahamic books letter system. And it made me this conjecture:

Abraham the prophet was the one who caused coming lots of prophets from his descendant just by establishing and teaching them a letter system to find god and the holy spirit meanings. For this conjecture, I had another reason from Quran: 2:124

وَإِذْ أَوْحَيْنَا إِلَىٰ إِبْرَاهِيمَ رَبِّهِ بِكَلِمَاتِ فَاتَمَّهِنَّ قَالَ إِنِّي جَاعِلُكَ لِلنَّاسِ إِمَامًا قَالَ وَمِنْ ذُرِّيَّتِي قَالَ لَا يَدْعُوا عَهْدِي الْأَضْلَامِينَ

And [mention, O Muhammad], when Abraham was tried by his Lord with commands and he fulfilled them. [Allah] said, "Indeed, I will make you a leader for the people." [Abraham] said, "And of my descendants?" [Allah] said, "My covenant does not include the wrongdoers."(۱۲۴)

I guess that fulfilling words was the establishing of letters which we talk about.

After years I checked how we can create a letter system to describe how letters work together when we put them in a word; And I called these works Letter Theory. So when we say Letter Theory in this paper, we mean our works to find the system.

I can guess that science of the book that we have in Quran is letter theory as I see and can witness that the Abrahamic holy books are not simple scriptures and are from god or a mathematician or a logician or someone else and we have:

وَيَقُولُ الَّذِينَ كَفَرُوا لَسْتَ مُرْسَلًا ۚ قُلْ كَفَىٰ بِاللَّهِ شَهِيدًا بَيْنِي وَبَيْنَكُمْ وَمَنْ عِنْدَهُ عِلْمُ الْكِتَابِ

,[And those who have disbelieved say, "You are not a messenger." Say, [O Muhammad Sufficient is Allah as Witness between me and you, and [the witness of] whoever has " (knowledge of the Scripture."(۴۳)

رعد - 43

As I know. the scripture have been writed with proofs and upon self similarity and Abrahamic hioly books are not only news from god but they are proofs from god.

Why abstract algebra?

We want to talk about the system that creates words meaning by letters meaning so we mean: For every a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n that come from the alphabet set $f(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$. So we are talking about an algebraic structure (As we know: Any set, with a rule (or rules) for combining its elements, is already an algebraic structure^[11]. So one of the scopes that we search in letter theory is Algebraic Theology.

Letter theory:

My inspiration comes from the Hebrew Tanakh and especially Quran; So like what we do in Arabic we assume three-letter words (Arabic roots) as the main words. Clearly, if we assume 22 letters we will have $22^3 = 10648$ main roots.

To start the theory and its fundamental elements I should introduce some definitions.

Kadition: If two Arabic roots have two and only two same letters with the same order in the word we call them Kad roots for example "RML" and "NML" are kad roots but "RML" and "MRL" are not. We call this relation Kadition.

Clearly kadition is not transitive for example "RML" and "NML" are kads and "NML" and "NMK" are kads too but "RML" and "NMK" are not kads.

We could call Kadition Neighbourhood.

Relation: The difference in the meaning of two roots, letter, word or sentences are their relation. This can be a letter, word, sentence or an infinity series of sentences. For example when we say "g" and "h" have "r" relation that means $g=rh$ (or means $h=rg$) and that means we can change "rh" with every "g" we see in our words or sentences.

Example: "g" is tool of "h" so the relation between them is "tool" and we show it: $g=rh$, $r=tool$

Transitivity: For creating words from main parameters we assume transitivity for our system so when we say "g" is tool of "h" and "h" is increaser of "w" we say "g" is tool of increaser of "w".

Lets write what we assume:

A: Alphabet set with three (or four) axioms (we discuss already or later about the reason that we choose these axioms) associativity, invertibility and identity (and transitivity).

W: Words set

L: Language set (its a group)

Set A creates W by a binary, trinary (or even more) operation and set W creates L.

$A.A \rightarrow W$ $A.A.A \rightarrow W$ and

$W.W \rightarrow L$ $W.W.W \rightarrow L$ and

I searched and asked lots of mathematicians to find out what we call sets like A but seems there is no name for these group creators so lets call them group creators.

In letter theory, there is no difference between relation and letter and every letter can role as a relation between two or more parameters. For example when in normal mathematics we say number its something different from multiplication but in letter theory relations come from letters; That means numbers are somethings different from operations and functions but in letter theory there is no difference between them and our set is set of everything and we study their relations basically. I mean in the

mathematics of letters there is no difference between relation and member of a set; members can role as relations.

Now we are in the situation that we can introduce our main work in letter theory and that is Letter System.

Letter System: If we have a language that all of its kad words have the same relation than their letters, we call the language letter system owner language.

It means:

For every a, b, c, d, e, f that comes from a language's Alphabet set if we have:

$$abc/ebc = adf/edf$$

Then the language owns a letter system.

Example: "RML" is tool of "NML" so if it is from a letter system owner language "r" must be tool of "n" ; clearly that means all of its words with "r" and "n" and just "r" and "n" difference in writing, must have "tool" relation in meaning. We say if a letter like "r" have x relation with a letter like "n" then for every "b" and "c" which come from our letter set we will have: "rbc" is x of "nbc".

Conjecture: The Arabic Quran has been written by a letter system (I do not say why is this my conjecture in this place of work (I only define the theory here. For evidence that I have you should check my theologian works.) but it is good for interesters to work on it). By assuming this conjecture we have a great course to work on in Quran. For example when we have OLM by QLM that means "q" is tool of "o". By writing such relations we can have great incomes.

Kad roots program: Find all relations of Quran and other original Abrahamic holy books kad roots.

Theorem: In a letter system owner language if the number of letters be "n" so at least "n-1" of letters have meaning.

Proof: We assume that one word has not any meaning, (As up to now we have no reason for the meaning of any letter) then we write the relation of other letters (they are n-1 letters) with it, clearly their meaning will be:

(their relation). (the meaningless letter) = their relation

We call the meaningless letter identity element. (That will be a dynamic identity element for example assume this set [-3,-2,-1,0,1,2,3] under addition as an operation clearly 0 is our identity element but we can assume that 2 is our identity element and define our set

as $[-5,-4,-3,-1,0,1]$ (Our identity element is relative). (You should know we already assumed associative axiom for our system and identity element is the second element that we have there from abstract algebra.)

So if we talk about such languages, We are sure that their letters (except one) will have meaning.

It's too important that we write letter relations only by identity element to avoid memorizing too many relations between every two letters (it will be $(n)(n-1)$ relations between letters).

When we focus on identity element we can understand its importance for our system; its an element which we find every letter meaning by finding its relation. We have two options:

1. To put our identity element in our letters set
2. To assume it in the out of our letters set

If we have a language that uses option 2 and we don't know its letters meaning we have a hard work or maybe impossible work to find letters meaning. Because we can not compare our letters with any meaningless letter to find their meaning (Its a good course for interested researchers to assume option 2 and find what happens).

If we remember our first conjecture, one of our goals is to discuss about holy books system.

Now a question:

If the Arabic of Quran has a letter system; Has this system an identity element in its letters set?

I have not any proof but some interesting points show us that probably Abrahamic letter system identity element is the first letter of the set which we call aleph الف

Some interesting points about Aleph:

_Aleph is the first letter.

_Aleph has not any sound (The sound of every alphabet letter comes from its first letter and the first letter of aleph has no sound exactly like its meaning.

_Aleph is a mediator letter in Sefer yetzira and we can mean mediator as identity element.

It is so functional for us when we want to work on Quran If our conjecture about aleph be true, then we can easily find letter meanings by using kad words which one of them has aleph and another one something else instead of aleph. For example:

امر و حمر

Program: Find relations between aleph and other letters by using kad roots which have aleph differences.

For example, find the relation of:

امر و حمر

Prime letters or Divisible letters?

We know that we are working on a system with meaningful letters that create meaningful words by combining their meaning; so words meanings are divisible but here is another question:

Are the letters divisible too?

If we assume our letters are "Prime letters" and we have not their inverses in our set, then the relation of every two letters will be irrational and we need infinite letters and words to define relations. So we are interested in "Divisible letters" or if we set prime ones we need inverses for every letter. We will show that Abraham the prophet has set "Divisible letters" and invertibility axiom both for his system.

Order of letters in roots:

In the Abrahamic letter system, different orders of three-letter roots make different meanings for example RML is not equal to MRL. Lets check Sepher Yetzieah to find whats different meanings of 6 permutations of three fixed letters in root:

According to Sepher Yetzirah, chapter 2, 29:

IHV means height. IVH means depth. HIV means east. HVI means west. VIH means south. VHI means north.

So in the Abrahamic system changing the place of the second and third letter in a root makes the meaning the opposite and we have:

For every X,Y,Z from our letter set: XYZ is the opposite of XZY.

Proof: For every X,Y,Z from our set we write them by their relation with I,H,V. So we put: X=rI, Y=sH, Z=tV and we will have:

XYZ=rst.IHV=rst.Height

and by the same way: XZY=rst.Depth, YXZ=rst.East, YZX=rst.West, ZXY=rst.South, ZYX=rst.North

We can put k=rst

So, every one of the six permutations of every three-letter root is one of three dimension directions multiplied by K(as a fixed meaning).

They will be three opposite pairs.

In the proof, there is an important point.

srt=str=trs=tsr=rst=rts because we still have not put them in a root and they are just meanings but SRT will not be the same because it has an order plus its letter meanings. Even when we talk about AAA it has 6 directions but because its identity element of the roots set its directions have no meaning too. The readers maybe ask whats the difference between ASA and SAA and AAS because they are all s.AAA the answer is that 3D directions have no difference and we just know them by their relationship with other things and they are not absolutes but relatives.

Letter equations:

We can simulate our sentences to polynomilas and letter equations when they are isomorphic to them and isomorphism is the tool and the connection between every two unfamiliar system for example the answers of the polynomial $x^4-1=0$ have isomorphism with North, West, South, East. And thus we use them to simulate 2D Cartesian coordinates or we use quaternions for 4D. Now by the information that we have about letters we introduce letter equations.

As I said one of our goals is to prove our sentences in our letter system owner language and I show that it is possible in the Abrahamic letter system. According to Sepher Yetzira if we put inverse letters to our system then we can do it easily. When our sentence is simplified to identity element it shows us that is a true sentence for example:

East of the west is the center.

Center is the identity element and east is the inverse of west.

Or for example:

Northeast of southwest is the center

Its a true sentence too, because its simplified version is our identity element (center).

In the Abrahamic letter system, we have these inverses according to Sepher Yetzira

As we know 6 letters make $i, j, k, -i, -j, -k$ if the first three letters (a, sh, m) be the identity, 1, -1 then we can say that we have group of quaternions inside the alphabet set by the 8 letters that role as: $i, j, k, -i, -j, -k, -1, 1$ and the important point is that we have some new letter equations which make equal words like: $i^2=j^2=k^2=-1$ or $ji=i^3j$ or $i^4=1$ and etc. So for example if i stands for ב and j stands for כ then: $\text{ביבכ}=\text{כב}$

One of our programs in letter theory is to find isomorphic images of numeral equations by letters equations.

Seeing everything a one thing that expand itself is what I think monotheism proposes, and we create all of holy books by just a single letter Aleph, And we say we should work on algebra by such way, but now I want to point to physics by the way and show its connection with letter theory, Assume that nothing has been created and there is just one material with one property: Divisibility to two similar material. Clearly this material expand itself to infinity materials without needing anything like god or an exterior help. Now assume that material without that property, God makes an exactly material like it, In the first episode the material of the world was fixed but in the second god made it Double, Quadruple, eight times,... . But there is a question: While the amount of the second universe is infinity times of the first whats the actual difference between these two? We can not reason that the second is infinity times of the first and we should assume them equal so we say that: Size is not absolute but relative, So to divide and to multiply are the one definition when we work on meta structures! and the universe have no size and size is what we assume for the subsets compare to the main set or the other subsets (I should add that also infinity is not absolute but relative We can assume that size of the universe is infinity times of itself). its exactly the idea of metamathematics via letter theory that I work on (the question is whats limiters? and do limiters can specify answer of every question?, Now by knowing this look at the below theorem in letter theory:

Theorem: By the three axioms every letter can be defined by a finite number of other letters.

Proof: Let us have "g" as our chosen letter,

Now we have an identity element in our set so we can write

$$g=ge$$

and we have inverses in our set so we can write

$$g=gff'$$

and we have associativity so we can write

$$g=(gf)f'$$

and its a new word and a new definition for our main letter

Now we can change every letter of our result in the same way and expand it to infinite.

So letters are not atoms and every letter has infinite definitions in our letter system with the three axioms.

We can expand it to have a greater result which will be profitable to understand the holy books speech system:

Assume the definition of a letter for example $k=bit$

Now change its letters (b.i.t) by their definition (as we proved every letter has an infinity definition);

If our new definitions had repetitive letters use your old (primary) definitions for them and if letters were new, use every finite definition that you want, For example, if you defined $k=bit$ you should define later "k"s that appear "bit" too.

Continue this algorithm to somewhere we don't see any new letter (simply because our set of letters is finite we will gain this level).

Now cause of our repetitive definition of letters, we face a self-similar object.

By changing our primary definitions for letters we would have infinity fractal shapes for our letters;

So we have a new theorem

Theorem: With the three axiom every letter has infinity fractal shapes of infinity letters.

Adding this theorem to our first conjecture means Quran and holy books are self-similar texts It can be a functional theorem to find holy books meanings however we don't use this theorem in holy books here and that work is out of our discussion here. But its a mathematical theorem that shows if Quran has a letter system with the three axioms

then it is a fractal book (also I should add when we assume the three axioms and look at the set of all words, letters and sentences of our language we clearly should say that our language set is a group) and we already know that prophets use similarities to say their thoughts like what Jesus christ used to use and 12 apostles said why do you use complex examples:

Matthew 13:34, KJV: All these things spake Jesus unto the multitude in parables; and without a parable spake he not unto them:

So once again we can empower our conjecture that holy books have been based on the letter system. We should add: Fractals are not just the language of the nature but language of holy books which prophets say have come from god the Creator. As a result, lets check a proof that Quran brings:

Proof of hereafter by self-similarity:

If the world be a fractal (by Mandelbrot's works^[4] we have this conjecture), then we can prove that hereafter comes; similar to coming day after night and spring after winter. Cause of self-similarity we should have the same pattern for the whole world which kills and revives us like earth in winter and spring so we have this in our fractalist Quran:

Quran,19:30:

يُخْرِجُ الْحَيَّ مِنَ الْمَيِّتِ وَيُخْرِجُ الْمَيِّتَ مِنَ الْحَيِّ وَيُحْيِي الْأَرْضَ بَعْدَ مَوْتِهَا ۗ وَكَذَٰلِكَ تُخْرَجُونَ

He brings the living out of the dead and brings the dead out of the living and brings to (And thus will you be brought out.(¹⁹ life the earth after its lifelessness

Quran, 45:5:

وَإِخْتِلَافِ اللَّيْلِ وَالنَّهَارِ وَمَا أَنْزَلَ اللَّهُ مِنَ السَّمَاءِ مِنْ رِزْقٍ فَأَحْيَا بِهِ الْأَرْضَ بَعْدَ مَوْتِهَا وَتَصْرِيفِ الرِّيَّاحِ آيَاتٍ لِّقَوْمٍ يَعْقِلُونَ

And [in] the alternation of night and day and [in] what Allah sends down from the sky of provision and gives life thereby to the earth after its lifelessness and [in His] directing of (the winds are signs for a people who reason.(⁵

اثبات قيامت:

فرض: جهان فراکتال است

قضیه: در هر فراکتال الگوی زیرمجموعه از الگوی مجموعه اولیه تبعیت می کند

مرگ و زندگی در بهار و زمستان وجود دارد بنابراین کیهان نیز دارای چنین الگویی خواهد بود که انسان ها در آن خواهند مرد و دوباره زنده خواهند شد

Difference between Homomorphism and similarity:

When we talk about similarity we say: $f(x)f(y)=s.f(xy)$ (if $s=1$ (identity element) then similarity is homomorphism. So close to homomorphism definition, "s"=deminsion of similarity for example: natural numbers are similar to even natural numbers under multiplication with $s=2$. For example: $f(2)f(3)=4.6=2.12=2.f(6)$.

Natural numbers are similar to even natural numbers under addition when $f(x)$ is additive for example $f(x)=x+1$

Isomorphism and similarity are two keys that we use to simulate.

Fundamental correspondence:

(How to establish a letter system on a fractal set (whether be a shape or language or something else))

Fundamental correspondence (fundamental isomorphism) is a good test for the theory and shows what theory creates if is true; The correspondence that we want to point to, shows us a correspondence between shape of Quran and letter systems.

Whether Abrahamic holy texts have a letter system or not, we can establish a letter system for every fractal existence. In other words, every fractal system is definable by a letter system. Every fractal existence has two sets: 1: the set of primary elements and 2: the set of relations (most of the time this set has just one member)

By multiplying set of relations by primary elements, we create submembers set which are similar to the primary set. (Every similarity is a sub-isomorphism I mean similarity is a kind of isomorphism.)

Now assume our primary set be our primary alphabet members and the relations be our set of secondary alphabet members, By writing them near each other in a word we will have a letter system.

For example:

Assume that the set of [father, mother, children] be similar to the set of [farmer, field, tree] it means: if $father.s=mother$ and $father.m=children$ then: $farmer.s=field$ and

farmer.m=tree

and we have father.r=farmer

Then we can call the relation of these two sets "r" because the relation of members is fixed as "r" (because these two sets are fractals) then we can call the second set [rfather, rmother, rchildren] (I have already written and followed a wide program on writing similar sets of quran^{[8][9]}).

Then if we call the first set [a, sa, ma] the second will be [ra, rsa, rma].

What I actually try to say is:

sr=s.r then f(sr)=f(s)f(r)

So the letter system is isomorphic to style of holy book texts.

(Some similar sets that Abrahamic holy books use: (prophet, imam, holy text, believers) is similar to (father, mother, sperm, children) to (farmer, field, water, tree) and etc (We need the complete table of these sets and its an important program for us to classify all of similar sets of Quran).

Let see an small part of the table of similarities that we can see or exists in Quran:

Father	Mother	Children	Milk	Adulterer	Bastard	Intercourse
Farmer	Farm‡	Plants	Water	Enemy†	Tare†	Planting
Pen	Paper	Text	Ink	Dirty hand	Dirt	Writing
Prophet	Imam*	Believers	Quran	Satan	Misunderstander	Teaching
a	b	c	d	e	f	h
koa★	kob	koc	kod	koe	kof	kog
Seller	Buyer	Benefit (AGR)		Fraudster	Loss	Business (TGR)

†According to Matthew 13:26-28

‡According to Quran 2:223 (Your women are a tilth for you)

*In Arabic Imam and Mother have a same root (AMM) and in Quran 33:6, God has emerged mother word instead of imam word^{[8][9]}.

★In this line for every "k" and "o" that come from the alphabet set we can write a line like this, I added this line to show what I mean when I talk about the fundamental correspondence.

So if we have two similar sets we can create a letter system for them and this shows a fundamental correspondence between holy books style of writing and letter systems; and it is another reason that we think Abrahamic holy books have letter systems and Abrahamic prophets expand their thoughts under letter systems; and its expanding by meaning and I have some examples that Quran expand itself by its shape and words for example in the example below we see that a text has been inversed and has come in another surah (same colors mean inverses of the first text)

107 الماعون

أرأيتَ الذي يَكْتَبُ بِالذِّينِ [1]

Hast thou seen him who denies the Doctrine?

فَذَلِكِ الَّذِي يَنْذِعُ الْيَتِيمَ [2]

That is he who repels the fatherless

وَلَا يَحْضُرُ عَلَى طَعَامِ الْمَسْكِينِ [3]

And encourages not the feeding of the needy.

فَوَيْلٌ لِلْمُصَلِّينَ [4]

Then woe to the performers of duty

الَّذِينَ هُمْ عَنْ صَلَاتِهِمْ سَاهُونَ [5]

Those who are of their duty heedless;

الَّذِينَ هُمْ يُرَاءُونَ [6]

Those who make show

وَيَمْتَعُونَ الْمَاعُونَ [7]

And refuse small things!

Now lets look at its inverse in another surah:

70 المعارج

وَإِذَا مَسَّهُ الْخَيْرُ مَنُوعًا [21]

And when good touches him, withholding

إِنَّا الْمُصَلِّينَ [22]

Save the performers of duty:

الَّذِينَ هُمْ عَلَىٰ صَلَاتِهِمْ دَائِمُونَ [23]

Those who are constant in their duty

وَالَّذِينَ فِي أَمْوَالِهِمْ حَقٌّ مَّعْلُومٌ [24]

And those in whose wealth is a due known

لِلسَّائِلِ وَالْمَحْرُومِ [25]

For the petitioner and the one deprived

وَالَّذِينَ يُصَدِّقُونَ بِيَوْمِ الدِّينِ [26]

And are those who, of the punishment of their Lord, are in dread,

And its an example of multiplication one set by inversion (as a relation) that Quran has used. (In this particular example, the relation was inversion; but it can be a word or something else, like what we had about the similar sets.)

در مثال بالا دو ست کاملا اینورس یکدیگر نیستند چون به جای یتیم و مسکین از متشابه آنها سائل و محروم استفاده شده این مثل این است که خدا به جای امام ام می آورد و یا مثل اینکه خدا دو عبارت کاد به هم را به کار برده مثلا تمام جمله ها اینورسند به غیر دو جمله که اینورس هستند اما یکی متشابه است این دقیقا مثل این است که یک جا کفر آمده باشد و بعد به جای ف از متشابه آن که ب باشد استفاده شده و کبر آمده که باعث متشابه شدن دو پاراگراف می شود. این تغییر کوچک معنای دو جمله را متفاوت می کند چنانچه معنای کبر با کفر فرق دارد اما تحت رابطه ای کبر به کفر قابل تبدیل است. این تناظری دیگر بین سیستم حروف و سبک سخن گفتن خداست. همچنین این یک راهنمایی برای قرار دادن یک سیستم حروف روی قرآن است اگر از قبل سیستم حروفی وجود نداشته باشد چنانچه دیدیم ما دو پاراگراف را به دو کلمه ی کبر و کفر تبدیل کردیم زیرا با هم متناظرند بنابراین همانگونه که کلمات قرآن و حروف طبق جدول قابل تناظر با یکدیگرند جملات قرآن و حروف نیز قابل تناظر با یکدیگرند. سوالی که مطرح می شود این است که اگر جملات با همان کلمات اصلی و

متشابه خود دارای معنایی دیگر باشند و نیاز نباشد آن ها را به محکاماتشان ارجاع داد چه؟ هرچند ما می دانیم که ارجاع به محکامات حرف خود قرآن است اما باید این احتمال را هم مورد بررسی قرار داد. مثل این است که کلمه با کفر معنایش متفاوت است اما ما چون کلمه ای به نام کفر نمی شناسیم کفر را انتخاب کنیم.

(I should add that its clear that prophets have used this method (fractalism) to write their holy books for example we have:

Matthew 13:34, KJV: All these things spake Jesus unto the multitude in parables; and without a parable spake he not unto them.

and also in Quran 3:7:

He it is that sent down upon thee the Writ; among it are explicit proofs: they are the foundation of the Writ; and others are ambiguous (متشابهات similars).

Reffering Quran words to the table of similarities program:

As we knew Quran use a fractal model to expand itself and its words are divided under similar sets, now, here is a program: To classify all of quran words into the table of similarities that we had (by their meaning). After that we also can see if words already have a letter system(their meaning are fractal and we should classify them but if their letters have the same classification, then their letter system will be shown. I mean if AGR was similar to husband and TGR was similar to wife and this model also was for ASP and TSP and for other kad roots that star with A and T then A and T stand for husband and wife.).

Meaning correspondence:

In the fundamental correspondence we had that letter systems have correspondence with Quran style of speech and now, we point to another correspondence, The correspondence between words meanings and the table of similarities, for example, فزع، جزع FZO and GZO

FZO means the pain that comes from the husband and GZO means The reaction to the pain by the wife, So they are similar to wife and husband, And style of Quran speech apply this method so well and We had it on the article of similarities^[9].

Now we are in the situation to point to another important correspondence.

Cycles:

Cycles in the Quran speech style are so important and have a fundamental role, for example Quran uses binary cycles so well for example night and day cycle life and die, poor and rich and etc.

If you read The first pages of the similarities article you understand that we have pointed that The primary set of Quran have been based on a binary cycle.

Quran says you was died we made you live and we kill you again and revive you again and also says the earth was died we made it alive and we kill it again and revive it again

and also says you bring your money to poors and we give it to you again in hereafter but if you dont we have nothing for you in hereafter. Ita a binary cycle in the primary set of quran, and as you know all of Quran have been based on the primary set, but whats the matter? Another correspondence: (Before the binary correspondence lets talk alittle more about binaries, as we told, the primary set have been based on binaries and it make all of other sets on binaries too, it means we will have lots of binaries its another corresspondence that shows every set should have binaries and its what we see in the binary corresspondence when we look at changing the second and the third letters.

Binary correspondence:

There is a correspondence between binaries of the Quran and changing the second and the third letters of the words (as you know we had that changing the second and the third letter of the words make their meanings opposite for example MNO is opposite of MON. these kind of words have a dynamic cycle, when you active one of them now the other will be activated in the future, Its a method that Quran uses so well.

Now a big Question (before the question lets look at the trinary function)

Trinary Function:

Assume three words like MNP PMN NPM. There is a fixed function that make a cycle between these three, I mean if $MNP.f=PMN$ so we should have: $PMN.f= NPM$ and $NPM.f= MNP$ too. because there is no difference between their letters and the only difference is their order. It means there is a "f" in the letter system that $f^3=identity$ element.

So the big question:

Is there any Trinary cycle (look at the primary set)(like what we had about the binary cycle) that has a correspondence with trinary function? Without this we can not assume a letter system how we proposed. So we should check the primary set for the trinary cycle (function). Also as soon as we find the f we can bring quaternions and their rules in our works because $f^3=1$ means that we are facing an object that is isomorphic to quaternions.

The binary of Quran is cycle of life and death and their similars for example day and night, to plant and to growth, to copulate and to give birth. Now lets talk about 3.

3 comes in Quran when we talk about hidden process of child in the womb so I guess the trinary function can be inside of 1 of 2. And 3 for to plant and 3 for to growth completes the cycle, So the trinary cycle is not something new but something inside of the binary cycle but by a different partition; It means a cyclic group of order 6 however it doesnt satisfy us completely because we guess its not always cyclic and quaternions are not cyclic and we know that sepher yetzirah talks about quaternions and not about a cyclic group; But we have a great example for this that we guess at least we have one number of what we assume and thats 40:67 which it seems we have 6 cyclic or 6 elements of the quaternion group as we have (red words are what I mean):

هُوَ الَّذِي خَلَقَكُمْ مِنْ تَرَابٍ ثُمَّ مِنْ نُطْقَةٍ ثُمَّ مِنْ عِلْقَةٍ ثُمَّ يُخْرِجُكُمْ طِفْلًا ثُمَّ لِتَبْلُغُوا أَشُدَّكُمْ ثُمَّ لِيَتَّكِفُوا شُبُهَاتًا وَمِنْكُمْ مَنْ يُتَوَقَّى مِنْ قَبْلُ^ط وَلِيَتَّبِعُوا أَجَلًا مُسَمًّى وَلَعَلَّكُمْ تَعْقِلُونَ

We already know that cyclic groups need just one active generator to be produced but what if our group is not cyclic? Then we need at least two active generators and if (according to sepher yetzirah) we are facing some letters that create a quaternion then we should search for groups with two generators in Quran it means if we have "e" as identity element and our generators are "a" and "b" after "e" we can have "a" or "b" for example Torab (in 40:67 Quran) is the identity element and after it comes Notfe but if it was a quaternion it was not stable that after Torab comes Notfe and we had: After Torab we have either Notfeh (a) or something else(b). And as we see the example (Quran 40:67) is not isomorphic to quaternions but a cyclic group of order 6. Now we need to find a group with two generators in Abrahamic holy books.

Another big question:

According to what we had in the article "God Words..." Quran sometimes change the words with their similars, for example we know that r,b,t,c as a set then multiply it at f so we have rf,bf,tf,cf but Quran use rf,bf,t,cf; And its a question for us to know how is it mathematically work.

Six directions and sepher yetzirah's letter theory

Six directs have a essential role in sepher yetzirah, the book proposes six letters as six direction so its important to simulate six directs under matgematics to know their relation and also for the place of the three letters roots which have 6 permutations,the book says I,H,V and its six permutations has corresspondence to six directions: up,down,north,west,east,south

There is a noncorrespondence that need to solve in this proposition, lets start with simulating six directions: (its better if you know Hamilton quaternions)

North, up and east have a fixed relation between theirselves let call it f and north and south are opposite of each other let call their relation g it means:

$$N.f=U \quad N.f^2=E.$$

$$N.g=S. \quad U.g=D. \quad E.g=W$$

where $f^3=N$. $g^2=N$. and $fg=gf$

If we divide the directs by North we will have:

$$f=U \quad f^2=E. \quad f^3=e$$

$$g=S. \quad f.g=D. \quad f^2.g=W$$

As you see its a cyclic group and its generator is $fg=D$. If sepher yetzira and our operation be without any error then we must say that six letters under divide by k create a 6 member cyclic group and also we must say permutations of every 3 letter roots have corresspondence with 6 member cyclic group its what I have doubt about it because we expect three letter roots and their six permutations have corresspondence to group of permutations S_3 .

As we know groups of order 6 have two isomorphism: cyclic and S_3 .

If we assume $gf=f^2g$ then our group will be S_3 .

If the six letters have corresspondence to cyclic group of order 6 (6directions) then we should declare that letters are not atoms and we can create them by some generators we already know that every cyclic group is makable by one generator then we can argue that those six letters are makeble by one generator (and also the divisor element k).

دوری بودن شش جایگاه سه حرفی ها:

همانطور که گفتیم یک عملیات دوگانه در قرآن وجود دارد مثل شب و روز مرگ و زندگی و ... که مدام به هم تبدیل می شود و پیش بینی کردیم یک چرخه ی سه گانه هم باید وجود داشته باشد بین مثلا کفر فرک و رکف زیرا اف ثابتی بین اینها وجود دارد که از اولی به دومی و از دومی به سومی و از سومی به اولی می برد اما قضیه چیست، در سیستم های حروف بین دو حرفی ها چرخه ای دوگانه است و این قضیه متناظر با سبک سخن گفتن خداست و در سه حرفی ها چرخه ای شش گانه و در چهار حرفی ها چرخه ای بیست و چهار گانه و در پنج حرفی ها....

بنابراین همانگونه که ساعات صفر، چهار، هشت، دوازده، چهار عصر، هشت شب با هم دوری هستند شش حرفی ها هم باید با هم دوری باشند و چرخه ای و اف ثابتی آن ها را به هم تبدیل کند و معنی سه حرفی ها با اف ثابتی باید به هم تبدیل شود.

روش دیگر این است که سه حرفی ها مانند شمال جنوب مشرق مغرب بالا پایین عمل کنند که سفر یتزیرا این را پیشنهاد می کند و من نمی دانم آیا به غیر از این دو روش دیگری هم وجود دارد که بتواند در سیستم حروف قرار گیرد؟ و آیا اصلا دو روش مذکور یکسانند؟

ما باید در فرم کلی قرآن دنبال چنین چرخه هایی بگردیم زیرا اگر در فرم کلی چنین خصوصیتی تعبیه نشده باشد به بقیه ست ها نیز تعمیم نخواهد یافت

Do not forget that in a complete letter system, a set of relations must be from our main set (our alphabet set); Without this, we can not establish a complete letter system on our fractal system and our fractal system must have this axiom to be convertible to a letter system. In other fractals we usually know, relation (expander element) is not from the main set but in fractals which we can establish a letter system for, "r" must come from the primary set and every letter must can role as an expander element. So if we show that holy books sentences:

1: Are dividable to similar sets

2: Relations between those sets come from elements of the main set

Then we can establish a letter system for them even if we have not any letter system for them up to now.

These two are necessity and sufficiency conditions for having a letter system in holy books. We already know that the first condition is okay in holy books and the condition we must search about and find is the second; Also it made our conjecture stronger that: Abrahamic holy books have a letter system.

Do not forget that in three-letter roots the second condition comes twice; one time makes the root a two-letter word and the second time makes it a three-letter root.

Now lets look at the correspondences via diagram below

How to find similar words of holy books:

For this we also use self-teaching method of Quran: If two word have a same relation with a third word then the two are similars. We also can use what we had about maoon 107 and maarej 70 in the example aboves.

Numbers meaning:

Every number in Quran and in every holy book has a special equivalent word in the letter system; For example, 1 is equal to VHD and 4 is RBO or 7 is SBO. We already have said that letters have meaning in the letter systems, Now these numbers are inside of Quran as words and these words have meanings, their meanings are not just about their numeric value; I want to point to the some meanings of some numbers.

Is it possible to mean numbers in number theory?

When we say numbers have meaning they must have in number theory too; And I try to show the link of the two branch (letter theory and number theory(~algebra))

One is god, creator of everything and this meaning is not amazing for us at all, Lets talk about three: Three in Quran is always with secret, hidden and etc. you can see Quran 3:41, 18:25, 24:58, 39:6; Is there any relationship between meaning of numbers in letter theory and algebra? It means is there any isomorphism between numbers in letter they and number theory? for example $2 \cdot 3 = 6$ so: if three means hidden and two means plan does six mean hidden plan? My guess says yes.

Another question: Why does 3 means hidden? We know that its meaning comes from its letters but whats link between being hidden and being three in numbers?

Semi Letter System:

As we said there are two conditions for having a letter system, here I define semi letter systems which we can establish just by having the first condition and then we can establish for Quran a semi letter system because Quran is dividable to similar sets which means every fractal system (like Quran) is a semi letter system.

Assume the Alphabet set as (a,b,c,\dots,z) each member of the set has a meaning, now we have different relation which multiplies the set and creates a similar set like (ar,br,cr,\dots,zr) but r does not come from the primary set but we still use r by a different meaning then its a semi letter system; and its much easier than a random language without having a semi system. For example assume that (a,b,c,\dots,z) is our primary set we choose one of the members and put it as the first letter of our three-letter root, so in every three-letter root the first letter comes from our primary set and then the second letter is from the second set that its shape is like the primary set members but with a different meaning. Here there is not any relation between the primary set and the second set, so in every semi letter system that has n members for its alphabet set we have $3n$ meaning for its letters and meaning of every fixed letter like d when its in the first place of the root is totally different than when its in the second or the third place of the root. When the system is like this we call it a semi letter system. Every fractal object is a semi letter system but not necessarily a letter system. In these systems when we say abc its totally different from bac and cba .

Attention: If Quran has a letter system it is much easier if we firstly find its semi letter system and then find the second condition.

Program: Classify the whole of holy texts under a letter system (or a semi letter system) after describing their pattern of fractalism.

We should show that holy books (like Quran) have a primary set and all of their sentences come from this set or a specific relation multiply this set $(r.Set)$ and show that " r " comes from the set. This program is something that I have seen and worked on it and is the most important program that theology should follow. Its logical and mathematical theology and I have evidences that the set works like this and we have a letter system in Quran but I do not show my evidence here because its just its mathematics and I think the future of theology should be just mathematical if what I say be true. Do not forget there are two things:

1. Quran has a letter system
2. Quran has expanded itself sentences by a primary set (see [9])

And the evidences of these two is in my hand. (For option1 I showed in this article that if option2 be true, then we will have the option1 automatically or manually. So I just should show in another article(s)^{[8][9]} that option 2 is true and then it will be proof of 1 and 2.)

What we should add is that letter systems probably are the most complete forms of fractals that we know; Most of the time fractals have just one relation to expand but the letter system creates more relations by its primary set of letters and letters role as

relations in every complete letter system.

Analysis of formulas:

In science (physics, chemistry and etc) most of time we face functions that we don't know but the results; So there is a question: Can we certainly talk about functions that we do not know just by their outputs? In letter theory we have a similar question assume that the system that we study (in physics letter theory or etc) is a 2-degree polynomial, We don't know the identity of system but we have a,b,c of the polynomial, the other thing that we have is the answer of the system, it means we know what happens when we give the system a,b and c and there will be three clear x for us, our question is: Is this enough to know and solve the unknown equation? for example we know that the two x are fixed when we multiply a,b,c in every k and it's a limiter that we can find it easily the question is: How do we can find all of limiters for every formulas, and Are limiters enough to find a formula? If limiters are not enough then we can say that some of our questions in physics will not find any answer by the way we run, and identity of objects will be undefinable.

The other question is: How many ways we have to product a formula for n variable? If limiters work properly there will be just one. The program of analysis of formula was wide and I push it into another article.

تست مستقل بودن یا وابسته بودن متغیرهای یک فرمول،

این تست انجام می شود تا بفهمیم مثلا در یک فرمول سه متغیره آ ب سی آیا دوبرابر کردن سی به مقدار آ و ب هم ربط دارد یا نه مثلا در معادلات درجه ان اینها به هم ربط دارند زیرا بخش هایی از جملات در همدیگر ضربند
مثلا $4ac$

اما در سیستم حروف ذی پیشنهادی ما متغیرها مستقلند مثلا اگر ک با ف جایگزین شود تغییری در معنای دو حرف دیگر فعل ایجاد نمی کند اما معادلات درجه ان تمام جواب ها به هم می ریزد

Quaternions:

In sepher yetzirah we have that 6 letter create 6 geographical directions,

whats the difference between east up and north? they have no difference but near each other they act different, if we assume that north. $f = \text{up}$ then $up.f = \text{east}$ and $east.f = \text{north}$ so $f^3 = e$. Its exactly a quaternion ($-ijk = e$) we can say that ($-\text{north} = \text{south}$). $f = \text{up}$ then $up.f = \text{east}$ and $east.f = \text{south}$.

And we know to create a 3D stimulation we need quaternions that work in rings criteria. So our directions are equal to i, j, k, -i, -j and -k. What I try to say? we worked on a group and now we faced a ring; So we should check this for our letters that are our i j k -i -j -k when we work with them for example $ijk = -1$ and for finding meaning we should check

and apply this. The book (yetzirah) says permutations of h,i,v create 6 directions and directions are 6 letters so permutations of these three letter (hiv) create 6 other letters and seemes that (hiv) are our (ijk) in quaternions.

An open question:

From some sources, we know that some opposite words are equal by their number in Quran (for example if there are 90 days and 90 nights words in Quran) so inverses have appeared here too and we have a question here:

Is Quran a subgroup of the Abrahamic Arabic language group?

If yes, Why did Quran need to be a subgroup of Arabic?

What will be its benefit to be a subgroup?

Axioms of algebraic structures

Lots of topics that we discuss in letter theory may be meaningless in number theory.

We strongly want to know why group? why identity element? why inverse? why everything? Because we should create a good system for letters. Indirectly it can help us for number theory too.

In groups we have closure so we say for every a,b that come from the alphabet set $ab=c$ then c must be in the alphabet set. Now we know that inverse of c exists let call it k then we have $abk=ck=e$ (identity element). It says that some three letter roots mean nothing (identity element) if our alphabet set be a group. In the first insight you may think its wrong because it will made our vocabulary down to number of alphabet letters but actually the role of route is so important it means two word can have same result but from two different routes and routes are so important in the theory, for example $fdk=e=upo$ but upo is something different from fdk. 1.Qabel killed Habel, 2.Habel killed himself. Result: Habel have been killed but the two routes are different.

Langlands Program

As we know langlands program is a unifying program of mathematics, When we deeply look at mathematics and algebra we simply can see that selfsimilarity (automorphism) and similarity (isomorphisn and homomorphism) are the main ideas, my conjecture was that we can establish a fractal shape for algebra and observe all connections between their similar parts; and Galois theory is just one of them. Then we say a similar word:

Even if mathematics has not a fractal shape we can create for it. The Langlands program has a true connection with fractals and selfsimilarity of mathematics. Its exactly the main idea that we have for letter theory, holy books, physics and mathematics. All of science and holy books have been expanded by finite members and have been fractals. Lets point to an important inspirations of Langlands program: For example, in the work of Harish-Chandra one finds the principle that what can be done for one semisimple (or reductive) Lie group, should be done for all (Look at it deeply, Its exactly what we did to prove that hereafter comes because in every fractal, members are similar and if we have a rule for one of them we will have the rule for all of them. I explained about isomorphism and automorphism and their applications in letter theory in the persian version of this work. The reader should know that if two objects have same rules then they are similar and vice versa and if an object with infinity members is selfsimilar then its parts are simulators of eachother and the object. And we can use simulators inseed of them and its the main reason that holy books change words with their simulators for example in Quran 33:6 God uses mother instead of imam^[8] (Its the main idea that we use complex numbers for 2D and quaternions for 4D.

I want to describe the main program under the main conjecture: All of homomorphic and isomorphic images that we see in mathematics (~algebra) are subsets of a one selfsimilar subset. Its exactly how we see homomorphics in 1 2 3 ... n letters roots that we see.

If we can put mathematics into a self-similar shape and define a certain methodology for solving every question we can say that we have ended mathematics because we can solve every question then; Not right now that we proved Feats last theorem after hundreds years (Without having any gurantee).

Anti paradox program:

As I already have said some of the programs here and in the god words good understanding article, and as we discussed there that Quran sentences has paradox with hisself, sometimes even in two consecutive sentences or even a sentence with his self find the real meaning of every sentence (that has been changed with its similar) how we cant find any paradox even between two randomly selected sentences.

Some of the results:

Abrahamic theology should be studied by its mathematics (~algebra and fractal geometry (up to now)).

Abrahamic holy books probably have a letter system and if they have not, we can create

for them by two conditions.

Abrahamic holy books have been written under fractalism and what they say is provable via mathematics.

Alphabet letters of Abrahamic holy books are not atoms.

Hebrew and Arabic are mathematically groups.

Other major programs

Working on the Primary Set of Quran and how it works.

Finding ($F^3=e$)s(trinary cycles) of Quran.

Working on the self-similarity of algebra.

Converting Quran sentences to polynomials by their isomorphic images.

Working on solving polynomials by limiters and their relation with promorphisms.

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References:

[1]: The Quran, Available at www.mobinmobile.com

[2]: The Sepher Yetzirah, Translated by Wm. Wynn Westcott, Holmes Publishing Group, first published 1887

[3]: Bible, King James Version, Available at <http://bibleforandroid.com/>

[4]: The Fractal Geometry of Nature, Benoit B. Mandelbrot, W H Freeman and Co, 1983

[5]: Stekel, A., Stekel, M., Azaria, A., Evidence From Computational Linguistics for the Concept of Biconsonantal Etymons in, 2023, Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society, 45(45)

[6]: Bohas, G, Theory of Matrices and Etymons (TME), 2016,

Al-Abhath 60, 15-38

[7]: Newton, I., Motte, A. & Chittenden, N. W. (1848) Newton's Principia. The mathematical principles of natural philosophy. New-York, D. Adee. [Pdf] Retrieved from the Library of Congress, <https://www.loc.gov/item/04014428/>.

[8]: Mosleh, I, God Words Good Understanding via LetterTheory (July 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4512034> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4512034>

[9]: Mosleh, I, On The Primary Set of Quran and Similarities Program (August 5, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4532132> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4532132>

[10]: Mosleh, I, Metamathematics via Letter Theory View (December 24, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4674807> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4674807>

[11]: A BOOK OF ABSTRACT ALGEBRA, Charles C. Pinter, McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1982